

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING HUMAN RESOURCES AGILITY IN BANKS OWNED BY THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT OF SOUTH AND WEST SULAWESI

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine and analyze the factors that influence the agility of human resources at the Regional Government Owned Bank of South Sulawesi and West Sulawesi, namely PT Bank Sulselbar in Makassar City. The indicators of the factors measured in this study are the attitude treatment factor, the experience factor, the participatory advantage factor, the cooperation factor, the work design factor, the innovation factor, the self-development factor, the self-promotion factor, the level of focus factor, the systematic factor, the risk-taking factor, the professionalism, competitive power factor, organizational culture factor, and commitment factor. This study uses a quantitative descriptive analysis method and uses the SPSS application with a population of 336 where by using purposive sampling of 156 respondents from four divisions, including human resources division, back officer, frontliner and marketing. This paper using the slovin formula, a sample of 75 people was found. Results of this research, it was found that the attitude treatment factor, experience factor, participatory advantage factor, cooperation factor and work design factor were categorized as organizational factors and included in the well agile category. Innovation factor, self-development factor, self-promotion factor, level of focus factor and systematic factor are categorized as creativity factors and are included in the well agile category. The risk taking factor, professionalism factor, competitive power factor, organizational culture factor, and commitment factor are categorized as networking factors and are categorized as agile. All factors have been tested and have valid and reliable data.

Keywords: HR, Agile, Bank.

1. INTRODUCTION

The world today is in a state of volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity, which is abbreviated as VUCA. This requires all areas of life and social environment to make changes according to the demands of the times. Change is an absolute thing in a time that continues to develop as it is today. A research from Garcia-Muina et al. (2021), shows that the time span between the launch of a new product and its extinction from the market decreases every year. This makes the company's survival shorter. This is due to disruptions and changes caused by technology and customer demands. The effects of these changes occur all over the world, Indonesia as one of the developing countries cannot be separated. The changes were swift, like lightning and at the heart of it all was the VUCA era. Many industries are being transformed in this VUCA era, one of which is the banking industry which is required to be able to adapt to the pressure of technology, innovation, and competition both nationally and internationally.

Banking businesses in developing human resources in the banking industry have an important role in determining the achievement of development goals in general, especially as an effort to achieve social welfare and provide the best public services (Ciric et al., 2019). To do this, of

course, it is necessary to improve the quality of banking employees so that they can perform their duties as well as possible to accelerate the achievement of goals. Therefore, human resources in the banking world must have several characteristics such as high expertise and skills, broad knowledge, good talent and potential, good personality, motivation, morale and work ethic.

Facing changes in the fluctuating business environment due to the pressure of the Covid-19 pandemic, the banking industry must have the ability to adjust its human resources. The ability to adapt human resources can be achieved through the application of the principles of business agility (business agility). The concept of agility begins with the biggest challenge facing companies in dynamic global competition, namely how to achieve competitive advantage. Agility is the ability of the company's business activities broadly which includes the organization's ability to manage internal factors such as structural adjustments, utilization of information systems, management of company logistics and creating a mindset of human resources to be more agile in dealing with dynamics in the market.

To achieve these characteristics, the banking industry and its resources must develop their potential by participating in education and training programs related to their field of expertise. A job appraisal system related to motivation and career development for human resources in the banking world must be prepared. One of the banks in the banking industry in Indonesia that is owned by a local government must also have agile human resources. This is because even though the bank belongs to the regional government, in this case the provincial government of South Sulawesi and West Sulawesi, PT Bank Sulselbar has the status as a foreign exchange bank and continues to enter into a circle of intense competition with other banks that exist in Indonesia. PT Bank Sulselbar in Makassar City was able to become big, survive, and get the first rank as a bank with the best bank service performance in mobile banking in this era of disruption because it is considered to have competent human resources and is able to see complex and fast environmental changes (www.sindonews.com/topic/1541/banksulselbar). This phenomenon shows that the agility of human resources in the banking industry, especially banks owned by local governments, is also an important point in developing organizations that continue to be able to adapt to an uncertain environment.

The purpose of this study is to examine and analyze the factors that influence the agility of human resources at the South and West Sulawesi Regional Government Owned Bank, namely PT Bank Sulselbar in Makassar City.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Agile HR is an approach to human resource management (HR) that is based on Agile principles and practices. This approach emphasizes adaptability, flexibility, collaboration, and rapid response to changes in a complex and rapidly changing work environment. Agile HR aims to create a responsive work culture, increase productivity, and optimize employee engagement (Ahammad et al., 2019). In line with the explanation of Thani et al. (2022), that HR agility refers to the ability of human resources (HR) to adapt and respond to change quickly and effectively. This includes flexibility, the ability to learn and innovate, and readiness to face

challenges and changes in the work environment.

The benefits of an Agile HR approach include increasing organizational flexibility in dealing with market changes, increasing employee engagement, increasing work productivity and efficiency, reducing bureaucracy, and increasing the ability to innovate and compete in a fast-changing business era (Malibari and Bajaba, 2022). However, Agile HR implementation can also face challenges. Some of these include cultural changes and resistance to change, lack of broad understanding of Agile HR concepts, difficulties in measuring performance in an Agile environment, and choosing tools and technologies that suit organizational needs (Julian et al., 2019).

Factors that affect HR agility in organizations refer to elements or variables that have an influence on the ability of human resources (HR) to adapt and respond quickly to change. These factors play an important role in creating an environment that supports HR agility (Khambayat and PrajaktiBakare, 2019). Factors that affect the agility of human resources in an organization include internal factors and external factors. Of course these factors are also influenced by the individual concerned and the organization where they work.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research method used is descriptive quantitative by describing statistically by identifying in advance what factors affect agility (flexible operational ability to be able to respond quickly to environmental changes) in human resources at PT Bank Sulselbar in Makassar City. The indicators are attitude treatment factor, experience factor, participatory excellence factor, cooperation factor, work design factor, innovation factor, self-development factor, self-promotion factor, level of focus factor and systematic factor, risk taking factor, professionalism factor, competitive power factor, organizational culture factor, and commitment factor. The population in this study were employees at PT Bank Sulselbar in Makassar City, totaling 336 employees using purposive sampling from the human resources division, back officers, frontliners and marketing. Determination of the sample using the slovin formula, it was found that the number of samples in this study amounted to 75 employees.

The scale used in categorizing each agility indicator according to the Theory Planned Behavior from Ciric et al. (2019) are as follow:

- > 4 - 5 categorized as well agile
- > 3 – 4 categorized as agile
- > 2 – 3 categorized as less agile
- > 1 – 2 categorized as not agile

4. RESULT

The characteristics of the respondent data, which amounted to 75 people from the respondents of this study were 35 male respondents and 40 female respondents as shown in the following figure:

Picture 1: Gender Different of Respondent

Characteristics of respondents based on the age of the respondents can be seen in the following graph:

Picture 2: Respondent Age

From the results of this study it was found that data on participatory excellence factor, attitude treatment factor, experience factor, cooperation factor, work design factor, innovation factor, self-development factor, self-promotion factor, focus level factor, systematic factor, risk taking factor, professionalism factor, competitive power factor, organizational culture factor, and commitment factor were declared valid and reliable.

Table 1: Average and Results of Human Resources Agility PT Bank Sulselbar di Kota Makassar

Indicators	Average	Agility Conclusion
Participatory excellence factor,	3,91	Agile
Attitude treatment factor,	4,24	Well Agile
Experience factor,	4,18	Well Agile
Cooperation factor,	4,09	Well Agile
Work design factor,	3,90	Agile
Innovation factor,	4,54	Well Agile
Self-development factor,	4,08	Well Agile
Self-promotion factor,	4,00	Well Agile
Focus level factor,	3,99	Agile
Systematic factor,	3,87	Agile
Risk taking factor,	3,97	Agile
Professionalism factor,	3,95	Agile
Competitive power factor,	4,01	Well Agile
Organizational culture factor,	3,95	Agile
Commitment factor.	4,04	Well Agile
Validity	0,96	Valid

Source: Processed Data (2022)

From the results of the study, it was found that the attitude treatment factor, experience factor, participatory excellence factor, cooperation factor, organizational culture factor and work design factor were categorized as organizational factors and included in the well agile category. Innovation factor, self-development factor, self-promotion factor, level of focus factor and systematic factor are categorized as creativity factors and are included in the well agile category. The risk taking factor, professionalism factor, competitive power factor, and commitment factor are categorized as networking factors and are categorized as agile.

5. DISCUSSION

From the results of the study it was found that the organizational factors variables in this case were the attitude treatment factor, the experience factor, the participatory advantage factor, the cooperation factor, organizational culture factor and the work design factor belonged to the well agile category. These results are the elaboration of organizational factors according to Robbins (2003, pp. 794 -798) which includes first, task demands, namely the amount of tasks that must be completed by employees properly and correctly. Role demands, namely a situation where the tasks that must be carried out by employees are not in accordance with the position they occupy. These role demands can be in the form of role overload or the occurrence of role ambiguity. Role overload can occur when employees are required to do more than their

responsibilities. While role ambiguity can occur if the tasks and responsibilities given are not clear and employees cannot understand with certainty what to do. Second, interpersonal demands, namely demands created by other employees and have the potential to cause conflict. One example of this demand is the lack of support or motivation from other employees. The third is the organizational structure, what is meant by the organizational structure is the existing structure that will determine the levels of position or differentiation and determine the level of regulation (Baran & Woznyj, 2021). It is further explained that human resources can be agile to adapt to the environment, be innovative and effective in performing depending on the organizational culture (Naveed et al., 2022). Azeem et al. (2021), also explains that in this era, organizations will have a competitive advantage through innovative activities carried out by human resources through a series of organizational culture that become the order and positive habits of all human resources in interacting within the organization.

Creativity factors (innovation factor, self-development factor, self-promotion factor, level of focus factor and systematic factor) belong to the well agile category. According to Suryana (2006:42) the indicators of creativity are curiosity, optimism, flexibility, finding solutions to problems, originality, and likes to imagine. In another study related to employee performance in the research of Aprianggi et al (2018), creativity has a positive and significant influence on employee performance, where employees who have special skills in solving problems at work, so that the work done is completed on time and more effectively and also more accurate. Creativity is an important key for human resources so that organizations can continue to adapt to this VUCA era, especially human resources in the banking industry and other service industries are required to be able to increase business speed by focusing on processes and allowing high speed to occur at every level. Activities within the company (Perkin and Abraham, 2020).

Networking factors (risk taking factor, professional factor, competitive power factor, and commitment factor) are included in the agile category. In addition to conceptual skills, employees also need to be equipped with communication skills related to other people, which are also called human skills. Persuasive communication must always be created by managers to the subordinates they lead. Communication that is persuasive, friendly, fatherly and makes employees feel valued will make them open up to their superiors (McMackin & Heffernan, 2021). Communication skills are needed, both at the upper, middle, and lower management levels Bangun (2012). Furthermore, Gaol (2019: 484), describes that the ability to build networks by human resources in an organization is determined by their ability to build good professional relationships with everyone. Along with increasingly fierce competition due to rapid technological changes and a drastic environment in every aspect of human life, every organization needs competent human resources to be able to build good relationships between fellow employees and external parties in order to minimize conflicts and create positive value for the organization.

6. CONCLUSION

From this research it can be concluded that the factors that affect the agility of human resources at PT Bank Sulselbar in Makassar City are the following 3 (three) factors: the first factor is organizational factors which consist of the attitude treatment factor, experience factor, participatory excellence factor, cooperation factor, organizational culture factor and work design factor. The second factor is creativity factors which consist of innovation factor, self-development factor, self-promotion factor, level of focus factor and systematic factor. The third factor is networking factors which consist of risk taking factor, professionalism factor, competitive power factor, and commitment factor.

7. LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The limitation of this research is that the research object is still narrow. It is hoped that future research will examine the agility of human resources in the banking industry and other industries, and use the variables from this study to analyze the influence and relationships between the variables.

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